

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN PROTECTING THE RIGHTS OF REFUGEES: WEST ASIAN EXPERIENCES

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Abstract:

The world struggles to protect refugees' rights amid escalating conflicts and wars. Despite frameworks like the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, implementation gaps expose refugees to exploitation, and restrictive immigration policies limit asylum access in different parts of the world. Cases from Palestine, Syria, Myanmar, Rohingya, Afghanistan, and Ukraine illustrate these challenges. It is essential to strengthen the enforcement of international mechanisms for refugee protection via international collaboration. Some civil society organizations are playing a role in advocating for refugee rights. There are various gaps that require more coordinated efforts to address displacement causes and advocate inclusive policies.

Keyword: Refugees, Rights, International Convention, Conflict, SDG

I. Introduction

The Geneva Convention of 1951 is the most important international legislation for refugees. The Convention makes it very clear who a refugee is and what kinds of legal protection, help, and social rights they should have from the nations who signed it. The Convention also says what refugees must perform for the nations that host them and what kinds of individuals, including war criminals, do not qualify for refugee status. The Convention only protected European refugees after World War II, but the 1967 Protocol added to the Convention's

protections as the problem of displacement extended across the world. As of the middle of 2024, the global total of forcibly displaced individuals exceeds 122 million, including 43.7 million who are classified as refugees (Riseforhumanity, 2024). This figure encompasses individuals recognized under the UNHCR's mandate, Palestinian refugees, and individuals in refugee-like circumstances. Over the last ten years, the number of refugees has risen significantly, with a marked increase in both internally displaced persons and individuals seeking asylum in other countries. The Middle East is presently facing a significant refugee crisis, largely caused by ongoing conflicts and instability in nations such as Syria, Iraq, and Yemen. This crisis encompasses millions of internally displaced persons (IDPs) and refugees who are seeking safety both within the region and in adjacent countries.

Key Features of the Crisis:

Syria:

The civil war in Syria, which started in 2011, is the primary factor for displacement, with millions escaping the country and an equal number displaced internally. The conflict in Syria entered its 12th year in 2022, marking more than ten years of turmoil (TDG Network, 2024). Nearly 20% of the world's refugees are Syrians (UNHCR, 2024), with 6.5 million individuals residing in 131 different countries. A total of 13.5 million Syrians is displaced, which makes up over half of Syria's entire population, including 6.8 million who were internally displaced by the end of 2022 (TDG Network, 2024). More than three-quarters of refugees, or 77%, live in neighboring countries such as “Türkiye (3.5 million), Lebanon (814,700), and Jordan (660,900)” (TDG Network, 2024). Due to the tremendous strain this displacement has placed on host nations, economic and social issues have gotten worse, and the urgent need for international assistance and long-term solutions for Syrian refugees has been brought to light.

Iraq:

Prolonged conflict and instability have also caused extensive displacement within Iraq and into neighboring nations. As of May 2023, some 1.2 million people in Iraq are still displaced within the country, while the country is also hosting 273,700 refugees from other

nations (UNHCR, 2024). While the number of Iraqi IDP returnees stands at approximately 4.8 million as of May 2023, many of them face challenges with reintegration and still need humanitarian support.

Yemen:

The ongoing war in Yemen has produced a humanitarian disaster causing a lot of people to have to leave their homes. Yemen is one of the Middle East's poorest nations, and its violence has worsened its long-standing poverty and instability. In 2022, there were 4.5 million internally displaced people in Yemen, and these families were at a very high risk of starving to death (UNHCR,2024). Environmental catastrophes have made the hostilities in Yemen worse, forcing many Yemenis to move multiple times. The persistent conflict in Yemen has led to a humanitarian crisis and caused significant.

Historical Background

International and Regional Protections for Refugees

Human rights, humanitarianism, and state accountability serve as the theoretical cornerstones of both regional and international refugee protections. These rights result from the understanding that refugees are defenseless people who have left their home countries because of violence, persecution, or conflict. The purpose of the creation and application of laws and policies intended to protect the rights and welfare of refugees is informed by international law, human rights philosophy, and refugee studies. These important ideas include the principles of asylum, non-refoulement, and non-discrimination, which uphold the rights of refugees to apply for and be granted asylum, as well as the duties of states to provide for their protection.

The first such declaration for the protection of refugees came into existence in 1948. The UN Declaration of Human Rights was the first international declaration of its kind to provide protection and declare that the “right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution” (UN,1948). While The 1951 Geneva Convention and the 1967 Protocol explain more about the right to protection and what it means to be a refugee, the 1951 Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol form the international refugee protection system, along with various regional treaties and declarations. After

World War II, the 1951 Convention established international refugee law by defining "refugee," prohibiting forced return to places where their lives or freedom would be threatened, and establishing refugees' and signing countries' rights and responsibilities. The 1951 Convention first addressed World War II refugees. It defined a refugee as a person persecuted before January 1, 1951, and permitted governments to limit the definition to Europe. With newly emerging refugee crises in the 1950s and early 1960s, governments enacted the 1967 Protocol, an independent but integrally related agreement to the 1951 Convention that abolished its time and geographic constraints and applied the refugee concept to all qualified persons (UN). Refugees and their families have the same civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights as nationals under the 1951 Convention and 1967 Protocol (UN,1948). The 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the Cartagena Declaration on Refugees, the 1969 OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa, and the 1994 Arab Convention on Regulating the Status of Refugees in Arab Countries work together with the two instruments (National Immigration Forum,2024). Similarly, the 1984 Cartagena Declaration on Refugees outlines the protection of refugees in Latin America and the Caribbean. European Union (EU) Laws: Within the EU, there are legal instruments governing asylum and refugee protection. The main ones include the Dublin Regulation, which determines the responsible member state for processing asylum applications, and the Qualification Directive, which harmonizes criteria for recognizing refugee status.

The implementation and interpretation of these laws may vary among countries and regions, and additional domestic laws and policies of individual states might provide further protections and obligations related to refugees. Moreover, people are often confused between asylum seekers and refugees. A person who requests asylum is referred to as an asylum-seeker because their request for refugee status and rights has not yet been fully reviewed and accepted by the authorities. While asylum seekers genuinely qualify for international protection, this is decided by national asylum systems. Those who are evaluated fairly and are granted refugee status have access to the rights and freedoms guaranteed by international law (Ekmekci, 2016). The circumstances may be varied for different refugees around the world.

Challenges of Refugees in West Asia

The refugee crisis in West Asia poses a variety of linked challenges, including meeting basic needs, addressing the social and economic effects of displacement, and securing long-term solutions for those who have been displaced. Continuous conflicts, political unrest, and violations of human rights in nations such as Syria, Afghanistan, Iraq, and Yemen have resulted in mass displacement, leading to a humanitarian emergency.

a. Challenges Related to Basic Needs and Humanitarian Aid

Refugees frequently find it difficult to obtain fundamental necessities such as shelter, food, water, medical care, and sanitation. The influx of refugees can overwhelm local communities and their existing infrastructure, resulting in shortages and heightened costs for services like healthcare, education, and utilities. Humanitarian organizations encounter considerable funding issues as they strive to meet the demands of an increasing refugee population. Refugees, particularly women and children, face a heightened risk of gender-based violence, exploitation, and other security threats.

b. Social and Economic Impacts

Refugees may experience social isolation, face discrimination, and encounter obstacles in accessing education and job opportunities. Competition for employment, housing, and resources can result in tensions between refugees and local communities. Displacement and ongoing conflicts can severely disrupt local economies, affecting both refugees and host populations. Refugees might lose their residences, businesses, and access to traditional means of earning a living, resulting in economic difficulties.

c. Challenges in Finding Long-Term Solutions

Numerous refugees wish to return to their home countries, but this is often unsafe due to ongoing conflicts, the absence of infrastructure, and political instability. The process of resettling in third countries is complex and lengthy, with limited options available, leaving many refugees in extended periods of displacement. Achieving durable

solutions, such as integration within host communities or resettlement, necessitates addressing the underlying causes of displacement and fostering peaceful and stable conditions. Climate change and natural disasters are intensifying displacement and creating additional challenges for both refugees and their host communities. Persistent conflicts and political unrest in the region obstruct efforts to discover sustainable solutions for refugees and avert further displacement.

Regional Crisis of Refugees in West Asia

Palestinian Refugees:

One of the most complicated conflicts and wars is the Israel-Palestine conflict. Palestinian refugees' problem is the oldest and continues even in present times, getting worse with each passing day. The problem of Palestinian refugees begins by the Al-Nakba, which many Palestinians associate with the 1947-1949 forced emigration, also conjures up the full history of Palestinian displacement, which is currently going on in 2023. Even during British colonization, Palestinians were being forcibly relocated, and between 1936 and 1939, British officials may have destroyed up to 5,000 Palestinian dwellings (University of Central Arkansas, n.d.). Organizations like the Palestine Jewish Colonization Association and others have made it clear that the Zionist project has attempted to establish a nation through colonialism from the beginning (Manoukian, 2021). This violence has been and still is performed in the name of Judaism, despite the fact that for many years they displaced and oppressed others unethically in the name of the Jewish homeland.

The British government endorsed the creation of a Jewish state in Palestine. On May 14, 1948, the end of the British Mandate, Zionist forces declared the State of Israel's existence. This incident led to the first conflict between Arabs and Israelis (BICOM,2016). An armistice agreement between Israel and Egypt, Lebanon, Jordan, and Syria ended the fighting in January 1949. The Green Line, which is sometimes called the 1949 Armistice Line, is the border between Israel and the West Bank that everyone agrees on. Before Israel captured the rest of Palestine in the June 1967 war, the Green Line was also known as the (pre-) 1967 borders (Juliana, 2023). Israel's violent occupation of Palestine is the main reason for this continuing, devastating war that affects every part of Palestinian life. From 1947 to 1949, Zionist armed

forces attacked major Palestinian cities and destroyed over 530 villages (Haddad, 2022). A series of mass murders, including numerous massacres, resulted in the deaths of around 15,000 Palestinians (Haddad). Zionist military troops drove 750,000 Palestinians from their homes and lands and seized control of 78% of historic Palestine (Juliana, 2023). The regions are currently known as the occupied West Bank and the undersiege Gaza Strip were created from the remaining 22 percent (Haddad). Many displaced Palestinians became refugees in neighbouring countries like Jordan and Lebanon, facing ongoing challenges in accessing rights and resources. Many Palestinians who lost their homes became refugees in nearby countries like Jordan and Lebanon (Khalidi,2020), where they still have trouble getting rights and resources.

The problem of Palestine became prominent and well-known on international agendas only after the 1967 conflict. The dispute 'Yom Kippur' war and the 'six day' war were its two most significant wars. Even following the ceasefire, Israel and Palestine continue to have unfriendly relations because a number of peace conferences were carried out but unavoidably failed because of the parties' divergent views on the Palestinian removal from the occupied territories and representation. A significant shift in the state of calm came with President Anwar Sadat's historic visit to Jerusalem in November 1977. The United States and President Jimmy Carter took advantage of this chance later in 1978 to help organize peace negotiations at Camp David. Numerous peace initiatives since 1967 have failed. They reached the conflict's core issues and which, in the lack of, worsened the situation the discussions. Nothing positive has occurred in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict so far. Agreements that might result in long-lasting peace in the area (Fatima,2019). As a result of the conflict in Israel-Palestine it has created large scale displacement. When the “United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees” (UNRWA) in the Near East agency first started operating in 1950, (Hadassah, 2025) it was attending to the needs of roughly 750,000 refugees from Palestine (UNRWA,2023). Currently, approximately 5.9 million Palestinian refugees are eligible to receive services from the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near (United Nations Security Council (2019) East.

By the end of 2019, 79.5 million individuals had undergone forced relocation globally (UNHCR, 2020). According to UNHCR, out of 26 million refugees across the world, about 40 percent of them are children. The UNHCR was responsible for 20.4 million of them, while the UNRWA was responsible for 5.6 million of them (UNHCR, 2020). For Palestinian refugees, the United Nations and international law have established a continuity of protection that offers social services and protection through UNRWA in the nations where it operates and through the UNHCR in other nations, at least in theory. In reality, many nations may not always recognize that Article 1D of the 1951 Convention, which grants Palestinians the same rights and protections as other refugees, is applicable. However, UNHCR has repeatedly been asked to assist Palestinian refugees, especially during the 1980s, when many people fled the fighting in Lebanon for nations that were not UNRWA member states (Anera,2022). UNRWA depends on voluntary contributions from member states, which frequently leads to funding gaps and jeopardizes the social services offered to Palestinian refugees (Anera). It's the oldest refugee crisis. The Israel-Palestinian crisis still continued in present times. It has continuously killed and exploiting the life of Palestinian people every day. In Gaza children grown up watching inhumane treatment and are frustrated of the situation and feel helpless. The Escalation, violence and killings became a normal phenomenon while the rest of the world is living the fruitful life with all the facilities of technology. The consequences of continued violence will not be appropriate for the world. The neighbouring countries and most powerful nations should come up to stop the inhumanity against Palestinian children and people by stopping Israel to continued attack on Palestinian unarmed civilians on daily basis.

Economic and social crises brought on by world events may intersect with the consequent political actors. Indicators of poverty in the Palestinian Territories and horizontal equality between Jews and Arabs in Israel continue to be contentious issues. From a political and economic standpoint, violence is greatly influenced by poverty and inequality. The UN estimates that 36 percent of people in the Palestinian Territories live below the poverty line. These figures back up the World Bank's conclusion that COVID-19 and the war in Ukraine "amplified" the destabilizing risks in the Palestinian territories, where donor financing was insufficient to close the Palestinian Authority's funding

gap (Prospects for Escalation in the Palestinian-Israeli Conflict ,2023). A wide escalation could result from the interaction of a number of factors, including the economic crisis in Palestine, the emergence of new players, a disengaged U.S. government, and the absence of a political settlement.

For the of Protection for Palestinian refugees, this demographic stands out among refugees in a number of ways. The United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees (UNRWA) counts the children and other descendants of those who were first forced to leave Palestine between 1946 and 1948, when the state of Israel was formed; these younger generations are typically considered refugees in other displacement situations. Thus, despite the fact that the number of Palestinian refugees has increased dramatically over time, this growth has been caused by the descendants of those who were displaced decades ago rather than by recent displacement. And unlike other refugees, Palestinians are safeguarded by UNRWA, which was founded in December 1949 to give them direct aid and other services. As a result, they are not subject to the UNHCR's jurisdiction. UNRWA, unlike UNHCR, cannot resettle refugees; instead, it states that the protection and assistance of Palestinians is the core of its mission, "pending a just and lasting solution to their plight." The sole function of UNRWA is to offer services, primarily in the areas of education, health (including mental health), assistance, quick help, and microfinance. One-third of all Palestinian refugees live in refugee camps, which are not its responsibility and are instead managed by the host nation or governmental body (Nathan et al.,2023). Recently even United Nations has been attacked during the violent escalation of the conflict.

Syrian Refugees:

There is another war that has created largest number of refugees around the World. The Syrian Crisis has erupted while the President Bashar al-Assad, who succeeded his father, Hafez, in 2000, was criticized for excessive unemployment, corruption, and a lack of political freedom before the conflict (BBC,2022). Deraa's March 2011 pro-democracy protests were inspired by surrounding upheavals against authoritarian administrations (BBC).The Arab Spring rebellion quickly developed into one of the deadliest and most destructive civil wars in modern history. The battle has reached a bloody, protracted standoff in which numerous

military clashes are occurring concurrently, coinciding with worries about regional security involving Turkish, Iranian, Israeli, Kurdish, ISIS, etc (Petrini,2024). The civil conflict in Syria has developed into a huge obstacle not just for the Middle Eastern region but also for the rest of the world community (Panda,2022) The military conflict was the cause of the refugee issue, which cannot be resolved on either the domestic or international level even after a number of years have passed since the war began.

Due to the Syrian civil conflict, the number of displaced people has increased during the past 11 years (The Global Refugee Crisis, Explained. n.d . The Syrian refugee crisis is being called the biggest refugee and displacement disaster of our time. Since the start of the Syrian war, the people and permanent inhabitants of the Syrian Republic have been fleeing their nation. The United Nations says that 13.5 million of Syria's 22 million inhabitants before the war need help. One problem is that most Syrian refugees have either stayed in Syria as internally displaced persons and beyond the reach of international legal treaties or have taken asylum in neighbouring governments such as Turkey and Lebanon. About 6.9 million people are displaced inside their own country and more than 6.8 million Syrians have been forced to flee their homeland (Fatima & Rahman,2023). Most Syrian refugees staying in the Middle Eastern region. They are residing in countries for instance Turkey, Lebanon, Jordan, Iraq and Egypt, although about 10 percent have moved to Europe (Harrigan,2017). Turkey is home to utmost of the Syrian refugees (Atitwa,2018). Unfortunately, inhabitants and refugees in these nations live in perilous situations, especially as winter approaches. The infrastructure cannot handle displaced people. In the last decade, uncertainty, fear, and tremendous economic constraints have made women and girls more vulnerable. The child marriage rates have also risen among Syrian refugees.

Syrians have demonstrated tremendous fortitude over the years, but as the war rages on, optimism is dwindling quickly. Over 90 percent of Syrians are considered to be below the poverty level, and 12.9 million are thought to be food insecure (UNHCR,2024). Over 90 percent of Syrian refugees in Lebanon are thought to be living in extreme poverty as a result of the country's economic difficulties. Two big earthquakes hit southeastern Turkey and northern Syria on February 6, 2023. The 7.8 and 7.6 earthquakes shook south-central Turkey and northern Syria;

more than 50,000 people had died in Türkiye and 7,200 in Syria (Martin Mai, P et al., 2023). They killed tens of thousands of people and damaged many houses and other infrastructure. This disaster intensifies the challenges currently confronting Syrian refugees and those compelled to flee their homes in Syria (Atitwa,2024). UNHCR High Commissioner Filippo Grandi describes the conflict as "the biggest humanitarian and refugee crisis of our time and a continuing cause for suffering" because there is no end in sight to it.

Globally Major Hurdles of the Refugee Legal Framework

Lack of Access to Fundamental Human Rights: Refugees frequently encounter obstacles while trying to exercise their rights to work, healthcare, education, and other basic necessities. Often, their susceptibility to exploitation increases due to their fragile status. Refugees are vulnerable to abuse, exploitation, and trafficking. Furthermore, extended periods of relocation impede refugees' socioeconomic integration, which leads to mental health problems. Moreover, inadequate protection is required for vulnerable groups due to their special needs and vulnerabilities; women and children require special protection. Today's world desperately needs this sort of devotion, as we face several obstacles that both worsen the already precarious conditions that millions of refugees are attempting to live in and add to the rising number of displaced people. Violent and conflictual situations are becoming more prevalent and harsher, with a noticeable presence on practically every continent. Populist and xenophobic forces are becoming more and more prevalent in the international community.

It is challenging for people to request asylum, and it would be unfair for them to endure unfavourable conditions while detained or waiting for the host state to process their application. Refugees have the legal right to seek asylum, and that asylum must be granted in accordance with the Article 1A (2) of the 1951 Refugee Convention, A refugee is a person who is living outside of their country of nationality, is not able to receive protection from it, and has a fear of their persecution because of which they don't want to return to it (Convention relating to the status of refugees preamble, n.d.). Refugees cannot return home because they fear persecution based on various factors, such as their political ideology, nationality, race, ideology, and religion.

The history of the international refugee protection regime is both prosperous and troubled. It has been successful in providing international protection to millions of refugees whose home states were unable or unwilling to do so. Despite this significant accomplishment, the regime has on occasion failed to solve severe refugee protection issues and has been unable to implement long-term solutions for a significant number of the world's refugees (Keley & Durieux, 2004) However, in actuality, these people can seek more constrained types of protection. Individuals may request protection in this regard under the 1987 Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, Treatment or punishment that is degrading. This may be the case if the person's fundamental rights are in danger if they return to their country of origin, such as if they are at risk of torture even though they do not meet the criteria for refugee status. Refugees today encounter many challenges that make it challenging for them to apply for asylum. Refugee security has its limits because of how the protection standards in treaties are put into practice. Relevant parts of the way the treaty works are that the convention gives ambiguous instructions on how to make decisions, that the definition of a Convention refugee or a person who is entitled to international protection under the Convention isn't clear. It's not obvious what a Convention refugee is or who is entitled to international protection under the Convention, and the Convention doesn't provide refugees many rights. These gaps have something to do with the worsening conditions for refugees right now.

Way Forward

Since a stop to the newly forming wars is not in sight, it is apparent that as time goes on, many more people will be forced to flee their homes. Therefore, it would be prudent for all nations to become involved and try to find a solution. Children have suffered the majority of war's losses; many of them have been forced to become homeless, and a sizable percentage of them aren't even be able to attend school (Toroitich, n.d). In order for the Syrians who fled their homes to return, international organisations like the UN should work to ameliorate the situation in warring nations.

There is a need to increase public awareness of the difficulties encountered by refugees and push for a more kind and knowledgeable policy. International organisations should take part in advocacy campaigns to

increase national and international political will for refugee protection. There is a need to raise more money for humanitarian aid to address the immediate needs of the host communities and the refugees. The international community should investigate creative funding options and alliances to provide long-term assistance to populations of refugees.

There should be encouragement for the improvement of both domestic and international legal systems to close protection gaps for refugees. Nations should be urged to enact stronger, more comprehensive refugee legislation that complies with international norms. State parties can safeguard rights holders from corporate actors that violate their economic, social, and cultural rights. By putting in place the right laws and rules and keeping an eye on measures, by and ways to hold companies accountable for meeting and following standards.

According to United Nation (2020): Sustainable Development Goals and Refugee Crisis Management

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the refugee crisis are closely linked, with the goals aiming to make sure everyone is included, particularly refugees, while the refugee crisis emphasizes the pressing need for sustainable development. The Global Compact on Refugees openly connects forced displacement to the SDGs, highlighting the importance of global cooperation to assist both refugees and the communities that host them.

Interconnectedness:

Refugees and the SDGs:

The SDGs, especially those focusing on poverty, education, gender equality, decent work, and peace, are significantly influenced by forced displacement and refugee circumstances.

"Leave No One Behind":

The foundational principle of the SDGs, which is to "leave no one behind," requires that the unique needs and vulnerabilities of refugees be addressed and that they are included in development efforts.

Global Compact on Refugees:

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This compact foster international solidarity by acknowledging that sustainable solutions for refugees depend on worldwide cooperation and that neither refugees nor their host communities should be overlooked.

How the SDGs Relate to Refugee Situations:

SDG 1 (No Poverty):

Refugees frequently lose employment, livelihoods, and resources, intensifying poverty.

SDG 4 (Quality Education):

Children and youth who are refugees often encounter obstacles to accessing education, underscoring the necessity for inclusive education systems.

SDG 5 (Gender Equality):

Women and girls make up a considerable segment of the forcibly displaced population and face distinct vulnerabilities and challenges.

SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth):

Refugees may experience discrimination in the job market, which restricts their access to decent employment and economic prospects.

SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities):

Tackling inequalities within and between nations is vital for both refugees and host communities.

SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions):

Many refugees flee from conflict, violence, or human rights abuses, highlighting the need for peace and justice in their countries of origin and places of refuge.

SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals):

Effective solutions to refugee crises necessitate international collaboration and partnerships among various stakeholders, including governments, international bodies, and civil society.

Examples of Refugee Inclusion in SDGs:

Refugee-led organizations:

These groups are essential in creating and executing innovative solutions for refugees and illustrate the potential of refugee leadership in sustainable development.

Sustainable solutions for refugees:

The SDGs can be utilized to advocate for policies that support refugees in becoming self-sufficient, such as facilitating access to social services, job markets, and protection from violence and discrimination.

Specific refugee indicators in SDG framework:

Including refugees and other forcibly displaced individuals in the SDG framework can guarantee their representation in global monitoring initiatives.

Conclusion

To begin with, the issue does not stem from the refugees themselves. Generally, they lack the ability to legally work in the nations where they are currently residing; often, they cannot even obtain formal housing. Furthermore, refugees are more frequently victims of violence rather than perpetrators. In fact, refugees are at a higher risk of facing threats compared to the members of their host communities, particularly women and children, who are often subjected to gender-based violence, exploitation, and assault. With few options for food and basic necessities, they encounter significant obstacles in accessing even the most fundamental resources. The primary challenge of the current crisis lies in capacity: Delivering essential supplies to nearly 40 million individuals while safeguarding their rights is a daunting task, to say the least. An additional complication is that the majority of refugees are hosted in neighboring nations that are also susceptible to conflict, violence, and instability. This makes it considerably more challenging to deliver aid and support to displaced communities. While temporary displacement presents its own difficulties, the ongoing nature of most conflicts today means that host communities with limited resources can end up accommodating refugee populations for years or even decades.

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